

Academic Activities of the 1st Group International Extenics Scholars

In 2006, Prof. Florentin Smarandache, Department of Mathematics, University of New Mexico, USA, had successfully introduced Extenics to United States, and issued some relevant papers in famous international journals.

In May, 2012, Prof. Florentin Smarandache, as the first group of international Extenics scholars, came to Research Institute of Extenics and Innovation Methods, Guangdong University of Technology to study Extenics for three months. During this period, he participated in the proofreading of *Extenics: Theory, Methods, and Applications*, writing papers about Extenics, and The 2012 Seminar on Extenics' Software development, organized by Extension Engineering Committee, Chinese Association of Artificial Intelligence and Research Institute of Extenics and Innovation Methods, Guangdong University of Technology. Prof. Smarandache, who studys seriously and actively, set a good example for us.

After back to America, he wrote a monograph, *Extenics in Higher Dimensions*, which has been published by America Education Press in the United States, at the end of 2012.

Now, he, as one of vice presidents of program committee on the first International Symposium on Extenics and Innovation Methods, is writing papers about Extenics, and calling on other scholars and has already participated in the preparation for the symposium, which will be held in Beijing, on 16-18, August, 2013.

<http://web.gdut.edu.cn/~extenics/News/20130313Academic%20Activities%20for%20the%201st%20International%20Extenics%20scholars.html>

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